

Research Overview of the Impact of Internal Control on Organizational Compliance and Performance

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Abstracts:

The paper reviews the research in the world and in Vietnam on internal control, the effect of internal control on the compliance and performance of various organizations. Also, provide future research directions for researchers interested in internal control

Keywords: Internal control, compliance, performance

1. Introduction

In Vietnam, in recent years, the issue of fraud, non-compliance with tax policies, legal regulations, and corruption within enterprises as well as among non-state enterprises, have begun to receive attention. mind of policymakers and the business community. Many research reports have pointed out the reality, causes and solutions to combat fraud, legal violations, and business corruption. However, the phenomenon of fraud and corruption in the business of the non-state sector (between non-state enterprises and within the state of non-state enterprises) has not been fully realized, yet. Appropriate attention (Dau Thi Hien, 2018). This situation may be due to poor management due to inadequate internal control leading to many serious business process errors such as commercial bribery, fraud, price sending and forms of corruption. The common is to receive commissions. The phenomenon of "sending price" in business negotiations also exists relatively commonly. Therefore, there is a need for tight internal control policies and mechanisms to promote corporate compliance, minimize fraud and corruption in order to create a healthy business environment and sustainable economic development.

In the context of globalization integration today, the number of businesses increases rapidly, and the competitive environment is harsh, in order to survive, businesses are required to control the costs of promoting their competitive advantage to have sustainable development in the market. Vietnamese businesses generally operate for profit, have good business results, and have high profitability. Especially for listed businesses this is very important because it is a necessary condition for businesses to attract capital from investors. Especially for listed companies the control system is mandatory in the organizational structure of the business. Under the Enterprise Law (2014), public companies must establish a control board (3-11 people). However, the phenomenon of corruption, fraud, and non-compliance with policies and regulations of enterprises as well as of the State is not good.

Corporate fraud, corruption, non-compliance is a core research topic in business ethics documents because this misconduct can have serious negative consequences for stakeholders (Davidson). and Worrell 1988), staff (Zahra et al. 2005) and society (Szwajkowski 1985). For a long time, scholars have focused on macro variables to find explanations for corruption, fraud, non-compliance with regulations and policies. They focus on national wealth, democratic institutions, colonial heritage and cultural influence (Treisman 2000, 2007; Fisman and Miguel 2006; Sun 2009; Mohammad 2013). Some corruption is related to the quality of political institutions (Lederman et al. 2005; Schatz 2013) and others attribute it too weak civil society and a lack of free press (Themudo 2013). These macro-level analyzes identify precisely the context in which corruption may arise, its institutional origin and possible solutions to the problem of corruption. However, such structural analysis focusing on macro variables would not be sufficient without understanding the public's and business attitudes and attitudes towards corruption and anti-corruption reforms. In recent years, a growing volume of research has begun to emphasize the importance of subjective indicators, arguing that they can give a complete picture,

giving an overall assessment from the The enterprise-level, the corruption and frauds in the business are also very interesting. Along this line, scholars and practitioners have noticed the importance of micro-level variables in understanding and controlling corruption, such as corporate perceptions and attitudes, in particular the system — internal control over corrupt practices (Margit 2010).

Studies on internal control in Vietnam are quite new; previous studies were mainly conducted in the form of research to assess the status of the internal control system of a corporation or a business corporation. (Dinh Hoai Nam, 2016), or the study of the influence of internal control on performance (ROE) in a specific industry (Dang Thuy Anh, 2017) has almost no studies to assess the impact. of internal control systems to compliance and anti-corruption in Vietnam. Moreover, the specificity of the internal control system is assessed for its effectiveness and compliance, so it is necessary to study the relationship between internal control and compliance as well as anti-corruption in Vietnam. The world studies on internal control systems are mainly those that assess individual internal control systems or assess corruption, take bribes, and compliance of enterprises separately using secondary data (Zhang, 2018) or studying an in-depth aspect of internal control is a culture promoting integrity to compliance and reducing inflation (Bussmann and Niemecek, 2019).

2. Research overview

Relevant previous studies in the world on the internal control system:

Angella Amudo & Eno L. Inanga (2009), Evaluation of Internal Control Systems: A Case Study from Uganda, conducted a study to evaluate the internal control system (IOS) in the evaluation of IAS in regional projects. public sector funded by Uganda by the African Development Bank, includes independent variables that are components of internal control (additional information technology (IT) variables under COBIT): (1) control environment, (2) risk assessment, (3) information and communication systems, (4) control activities, (5) monitoring, (6) IT. Dependent variable: The effectiveness of the internal control system. Moderator variables: authorization, collaborative relationships. The results of the study showed that the lack of some components of internal control (internal control) led to the ineffective operation of internal control systems.

Babatunde S.A & Dandago K.I. (2014) on "Internal Control System Deficiency and Capital Project Mismanagement in the Nigerian Public Sector." This study aims to analyze the impact of the lack of internal control systems on capital project management in Nigeria's public sector. The author tested a sample of 228 capital projects in the public sector and showed that the lack of internal control systems has a negative impact on the efficiency of project management in Nigeria's public sector. The author recommends and strictly observes the Internal Control System to ensure the interests of the community.

Adebiyi Ifeoluwa Mary (2017), with "Impact of Effective Internal Control in the Management of Mother and Child Hospital Akure, Ondo State." The purpose of this study is to examine the impact of effective internal control in management at the mother and children hospital, Oke-Aro, Akure, Ondo State. The results showed that an IWC was established in the mother and children hospital, OkeAro, Akure, Ondo State, and had a significant impact on the management, growth, and survival of the hospital.

Impact of internal control to the efficiency of financial management activities:

Some previous typical studies of Fadzil (2005), Brown (2008), Kakucha (2009) ... said that there is a positive relationship between the internal control system and the income of the enterprise (profit after tax).

In the most recent years, some typical case studies include:

Ahiabor & Collins Christian Yaw Mensah (2013) with the theme "Effectiveness of Internal Control on the Finances of Churches in Greater Accra, Ghana." Research results show that the existence of internal control activities in the church and this affects the effective management and use of church funds.

Babatunde's study, Shakirat Adepeju (2013), on "Stakeholders perception on the effectiveness of the internal control system on financial accountability in the Nigerian public sector." Results from the study show that Internal Control System in Nigeria's public sector positively affects financial responsibility. And recommend, the Government should apply strict penalties to increase the effectiveness of internal control systems in Nigeria's public sector.

A study by Zipporah (2015), entitled "The effect of internal controls on the financial performance of manufacturing firms in Kenya" to measure the impact of internal control on the financial performance of businesses in Nairobi, Kenya. The results of the study showed that the environmental control components, risk assessment, control activities, communication information of the Internal Control System have a positive impact on the ROA, while monitoring has the opposite effect. with ROA.

Christanti Widyaningsih (2015) on "The Influence of Internal Control System on the Financial Accountability of Elementary Schools in Bandung, Indonesia" through multivariate regression analysis, with the independent variable being the five components of the Internal Control System (control environment, risk assessment, control activities, communication, monitoring) and the dependent variable are financial accountability at elementary schools in Bandung, Indonesia. The results show that the control environment, control, and monitoring activities significantly affect financial accountability. While risk assessments, information, and communication are not significantly affected. The results indicate that an effective internal control system of schools may increase the quality and financial accountability.

Cornelius Kipkemboi Lagat (2016) on "Effect of internal controls systems on financial management in Baringo County Government, Kenya." This study aims to determine the effectiveness of internal control systems for financial management at the Baringo District government in Kenya. The study concludes that, among the 5 components of internal control systems, the control and supervision activities have a significant influence on financial management while the control environment and information and communication do not predict significant changes in financial management.

Daniel Kiplangat Sigilai (2016), with the subject "Assessment of internal control systems effects on revenue collection at Nakuru level five hospital." This study seeks to determine the impact of internal control, in revenue generation at Nakuru Hospital level 5. This study establishes if the absence of the above components contributes to the association with fraud, loss of business. income and embezzlement. Research has shown that the control environment, risk assessment, communication, control, and monitoring activities significantly influence revenues at Nakuru 5th Hospital in Kenya.

Mahmoud Ibrahim (2017), with the theme "Internal Control and Public Sector Revenue Generation in Nigeria: an Empirical Analysis." The results show that the components of the control environment, risk assessment, control activities, information, and communication have a positive impact on increased public sector revenue generation. The leader should establish a KSBB division in organizations. Internal control measures should be designed to ensure the effectiveness and efficiency, reliability of financial statements as well as compliance with laws and regulations. This will improve revenue generation, will ensure Nigeria's sustainable economic growth and development.

In summary, the above scientific researches are published in prestigious scientific journals all over the world and show that there is a close connection between internal control systems and the performance of enterprises or enterprises — public sector unit. In particular, firm performance is measured by profit, revenue, liquidity, ROI, ROA [Beeler et al. (1999), Jensen (2003), Ittner (2003), Fadzil and another partner. (2005), Kenyon and Tilton (2006), Brown et al. (2008), Mawanda (2008), Ndungu (2013), Nyakundi et al. (2014) Zipporah (2015)]. Weaknesses or omissions of internal control systems all affect the performance of businesses or units.

In Vietnam, the study of application of internal control systems in a specific unit, the industry has been interested in many authors. According to the author's research, in recent years, there have been many domestic

scientific research studies evaluating the impact of internal control systems to the performance of the unit, can summarize some of the following typical studies. :

Doctoral dissertation by author Vu Thu Phung (2016), with the topic "The impact of the factors that constitute the internal control system on the performance of Vietnam Electricity." The research results have shown the level of influence of each factor of internal control affecting the performance of Vietnam Electricity. In particular, the factor "Roles and powers of the Board of members" play the most important role, followed by the factor "Managers responsible for identifying and analyzing risks" and the factor "Communication. external power of Vietnam Electricity" are factors that tend to influence the performance of Vietnam Electricity.

Another study is the doctoral thesis of Pham Quang Huy (2015), with the topic: "Perfecting the system of state budget revenue and expenditure accounting in Vietnam". The author has assessed the current situation of budget revenue and expenditure accounting in Vietnam in recent years by going from the legal corridor to the detailed regulations. One of the solutions proposed to control the risk of budget revenue and expenditure that the author proposed is "... the leadership of public units should come to consider the whole organization to have a full understanding, from which promulgating uniform regulations throughout the organization, this will bring a strong internal control system and ensure that the organization will operate effectively and achieve the set goals appropriately".

The doctoral dissertation of author Nguyen Thu Hoai (2015), "Completing internal control systems in cement manufacturing enterprises of Vietnam Cement Industry Corporation" The author clarified the nature of internal control systems, factors affecting the design and operation of internal control systems, in the context of IT application.

Another study that is also considered is the study of author Nguyen Thi Thanh Huyen (2015) with the topic of Master's thesis: "The factors of internal control system affect tax collection activities at District 9 Tax Department" for It is found that all five factors have a positive impact on the efficiency of tax collection, of which the information and communication factors have the strongest impact.

In addition, there are quite a number of master theses with researches on the application of perfecting internal control systems in public hospitals such as the author of Pham Hong Thai (2011), the topic "Improving internal control systems in diseases. public institute in Long An province ", Cao Thi Thanh Tam (2014), the topic "Improving the internal control system of public hospitals in Tien Giang province," Vu Thi Thanh Thuy (2016), with the topic "Completing the internal control system for business activities at Children's Hospital 1" ... The results of these studies indicate that an effective internal control system will contribute to improving the performance of the unit. general and financial efficiency in particular in business units as well as in the public sector.

5. Conclusion

These studies have shown that internal control has an impact on the performance of specific units such as Zipporah (2015), Aristanti Widyaningsih (2015), Cornelius Kipkemboi Lagat (2016) Daniel Kiplangat Sigilai (2016), Mahmoud Ibrahim (2017), Vu Thu Phung (2016), Pham Quang Huy (2015) ... have demonstrated that internal control affects the performance of the entity and the performance of the unit is considered by profit and turnover. revenue, liquidity, ROI, ROA. At the same time, recognizing the role of internal audit, the role of risk analysis, appropriate information, as well as the effectiveness of preventive control on the financial performance of organizations.

Some studies, such as Babatunde S.A & Dandago K.I. (2014) show that public sector units with internal shortages will adversely affect the financial management efficiency and recommend strict adherence to internal control systems to ensure the benefit of the community.

Research results of a number of important domestic and foreign researches can help managers base on these to come up with appropriate solutions to improve their management efficiency. main. Because financial efficiency is the ultimate goal that all units are aiming at, in the context of full financial autonomy./.

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